

Synthesis and Characterisation of New Polyesters containing Azo Groups in the Polymer Backbone

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The interest in recent years in liquid crystalline polymers with mesogenic units as well as certain chromophoric groups in the main chain has been directed towards polyesters¹. Moreover, if the azo and the azomethine groups are present along the polymer bond axes, they can contribute much to the stability of the liquid crystal state². We reported earlier the synthesis of aromatic polyesters containing azomethine groups in the polymer backbone³. This paper reports on the synthesis and characterisation of aromatic polyesters containing azo groups in the polymer backbone.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of polyesters is outlined in the following scheme.

The inherent viscosities of the polyesters BPD and OBPD obtained by solution method were found to be 0.14 and 0.13 dl/g which is the reported range⁶, whereas that obtained through interfacial method were found to be 0.16 and 0.15 dl/g respectively. The higher viscosities were due to the fact that interfacial method is known to give higher molecular weight polymers.

The electronic absorption bands at 385 and 366 nm of the monomers BPD and OBPD corresponds to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the azo groups⁵. The bathochromic shift in monomer BPD is due to extended conjugation, which is prevented in monomer OBPD by the ether linkage. The azo group absorption in the polyesters BPDP and OBPD appears at 395 and 366 nm respectively. In the

ir spectra the disappearance of the characteristic frequency of the primary amino groups of the precursors and the appearance of the ν_{OH} frequency around 3500 cm^{-1} and electronic spectral data support the monomer structures. The ^1H nmr spectra of the monomers BPD and OBPD show resonances for the OH protons at 1.6 ppm and for the aromatic protons at 7.2 ppm, thus confirming the structures assigned to them. The ir spectrum of the polyester OBPD shows a strong peak at 1730 cm^{-1} corresponding to the ester linkage⁷. The polyester BPDP also gives a similar peak at 1730 cm^{-1} . The band at 258 nm in the electronic spectra of the polyesters is due to the ester linkage³.

Thermal degradation of the polyesters synthesised through interfacial method, corresponds to 10% and 50% weight-loss at 310 and 510° respectively.

However the polyester BPDP obtained by the solution method undergoes similar loss at 225 and 470° . Polyesters containing azo groups are capable of forming liquid crystalline polymers. Further studies on their liquid crystalline behaviours are under progress.

Experimental

4,4'-Bis(1,4-phenylenediazo)diphenol (BPD) and 4,4'-[oxybis(1,4-phenylenediazo)]diphenol (OBPD) were obtained by coupling the diazonium salts of benzidine (Merck) and 4,4'-oxydianiline with phenol^{4,6}. The resulting solids were washed with water and acetone, dried (i. vac. at 60°) and recrystallised from ethanol. Terephthaloyl chloride (TC)

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was prepared by refluxing terephthalic acid with excess thionyl chloride in the presence of traces of pyridine as catalyst. Excess thionyl chloride was then distilled off and the acid chloride was recrystallised from dry benzene. The solvents and other chemicals were purified and dried in the usual way.

The polyesters were synthesised by both solution and interfacial methods as reported earlier³.

The inherent viscosities of the polymers were determined in DMF (0.5 g/dl) at 25°, using an Ubbelohde suspended type viscometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer in acetone and DMSO for the monomers and polymers respectively, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Thermal analysis was carried out with a heating rate of 20°/min in air.

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References

1. "Recent Advances in Liquid Crystalline Polymers", ed L. C. CHAPOY, Elsevier, London, 1973.
2. "Polymers: An Encyclopedic Source-book of Engineering Properties", ed. J. I. KROSCHEWITZ, Wiley, New York, 1987.
3. R. MANI, C. RENGASWAMY, K. RAMARAJAN and L. RAVIKUMAR, *Macromol. Chem. Rapid Commun*, 1988 **9**, 417.
4. EDWARD ARNOLD in "Aromatic Diazo Compounds", ed. K. H. SAUNDERS and R. L. M. ALLEN, London, 1985, Chaps. 1 and 5.
5. A. RAWB and F. FITKO, *J. Polym. Sci. (A)*, 1964, **2**, 1925.
6. W. M. FARRECKSON, III, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1959, **40**, 399.
7. L. J. BELLAMY in "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd. ed., Chapman Hall, London, 1980, Vol II, p. 53; J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall of India, New Delhi, 1934, p. 143.